

INCENTIVIZING TEACHERS: IMPROVING TEACHING OUTCOMES IN BASIC PUBLIC EDUCATION

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The present study evaluates the reliability of teacher incentives in enhancing teaching effects in public schools at the elementary school level in the Accra Metropolitan Authority in Ghana, west Africa. It considers different types of incentives, such as financial incentives, grants, training programs, welfare schemes, promotions, and awards for recognition. The research reveals that merit-based motivators effectively boost teachers' performance and thus contribute to better teaching and learning. Nevertheless, other aspects like the availability of teaching and learning materials, quality evaluation systems, and good learning spaces are also important keys to improving the quality of teaching.

Keywords: incentives; learning outcomes; student learning; teaching challenges; teacher effectiveness

Introduction

Background of the study

Every nation's future largely depends on the quality of education provided at the basic, secondary, and postsecondary levels. Over the years, education has and continues to play a pivotal role in the development of all the sectors of the economy, from agriculture to health and everything in between. Through education, young people are trained to acquire skills and knowledge to develop their human resource capacity and solve everyday problems (Indrawati and Kuncoro 2021). Education promotes industrialization through technological development, mechanization, discoveries, and scientific inventions.

Owing to the importance of education in national development, it is prudent to give critical attention to the stakeholders and actors of education administrators, teachers, staff members, students, parents, families, ministries, etc., to ensure the delivery of excellence and maintain the national education standards.

A growing body of evidence supports the notion that teachers are key in what, how, and how much students learn. Passionate and effective teachers are the foundation of a quality education, which opens doors to a lifetime of opportunity (Gu 2023, 745–761). Research shows that quality teachers make the difference in students' academic performance and lifetime success (Haycock 1998, n2). That notwithstanding, over the years, teachers, who are the main drivers of

education, continue to face unfavorable working conditions compared to other working classes and professions.

Teachers are least compensated for their tremendous efforts and sacrifices in educating the populace, and this mistreatment, in the long run, affects their daily lives and their productivity at school. In addition to facing performance pressure from school administrators and some experiencing a lack of parental support, most teachers have had to deal with pay cuts, salary delays, and deferred promotions that have intense effects not only on their mental well-being but also on students' performance (Katete and Nyangarika 2020). Research suggests teachers represent some of the most woefully underpaid and least-incentivized workforce in most countries. Teachers in cities and rural communities face tremendous challenges, particularly development, poverty, and inequality.

The question is, what is being done to improve the many teachers? The significant responsibilities placed on teachers and their expected productivity are not commensurate with the rewards and appreciation accorded them (Ololube 2006). The growing worry of this phenomenon necessitated conducting this current study.

A substantial body of literature and scholarship has highlighted many factors/barriers that impede the performance of teachers in the classroom, the most common of which are the sort of budgetary prioritization available to teachers, a lack of training, overburdened workload, and minimal or no existing incentives—extrinsic, and sometimes, intrinsic, in the profession. At all

levels of education, incentives have been noted as the key motivating factor influencing teachers to improve their teaching and, by extension, improve teaching and learning outcomes (Han and Yin 2016). It has been asserted that the best way to motivate professors to improve their teaching is by creating an equitable system of rewards for excellence and effectiveness in teaching (Chakraborty and Biswas, 2020).

Statement of the problem

Deplorable working conditions of teachers have been one of the factors stifling the delivery of quality education at all levels in the country. Most teachers lack the requisite teaching tools, receive low salaries, and experience poor health care (Darling-Hammond and Sykes 2003). Therefore, it is not surprising that teachers go on strike more often than any other working profession in the country. This occurrence usually affects students' performance at final exams (i.e., BECE and WASSCE). However, there are varying perceptions about the motivating and inhibiting factors for improving teaching outcomes and students' performance. Whereas some researchers do not emphasize incentives as a contributory factor to enhancing teaching outcomes, others posit incentives constitute an essential requirement for improving teaching and learning.

Establishing a cause-and-effect relationship between the effectiveness of teacher incentives and teaching outcomes cannot always be quantified or experimented with, mainly because of the unpredictable nature of human behavior and social circumstances that can equally

affect the performance of teachers and students. This study carefully traces the relationship between these two variables.

Objective of the study

The main objectives of this study were to:

- (1) To ascertain whether incentives improve teaching outcome
- (2) To identify incentives available for teaching in education
- (3) To identify incentives most likely to improve teaching outcome

Research question

- (1) Do incentives improve teaching outcomes?
- (2) What incentives are available for teaching in education?
- (3) What incentives are most likely to improve teaching outcomes?

Significance of the study

This study probed into issues relating to the effectiveness of incentives in improving teaching outcomes at the basic level of public schools. The study stimulated thinking and informed ongoing attempts by the Government of Ghana, the Ministry of Education, and the Ghana

Education Service to make resource allocation and incentives more suited to the challenges of teachers, especially at the basic level in public schools, and also to others at different levels in our educational contexts. This study shaped the discourse on the relevance of teacher-centered interventions for improving students' performance. The outcome of this study adds to the body of knowledge in basic education rhetorics and helps policymakers, teachers, school administrators, researchers, parent-teacher associations, and other education stakeholders.

Scope of the study

The researcher was restricted by time in extending the research to many public schools and teachers in all the regions of Ghana. The scope of this study was limited to data gathered from the ethnographic engagement and interviews with Mamprobi Sempe 1 Basic School Teachers. The study also synthesized case studies from existing literature and theorized the findings.

Research Methodology

Research design

According to Yin (2009), study design is the science and art of putting together the right procedures or arrangements that guarantee that the studies acquire more legitimate results. Cooper and Schindler (2001) contended that the research design is a plan that satisfies the

objectives and answers the research questions (Adekeye 2016).

As indicated by Ghauri and Grønhaug (2005), there are two fundamental methodologies in conducting research: (a) qualitatively or (b) quantitatively. Using qualitative techniques, researchers do not think about numerical data. However, in quantitative research, a significant emphasis is on numerical or quantitative data so they can be explored as much as possible without any predisposition.

The researcher used a qualitative data collection approach in this study to collect qualitative data that was empirically essential in assessing the effectiveness or otherwise of teacher incentives to improve teaching outcomes. The population target was Mamprobi Sempe 1 Basic School teachers from Class One to Class Six. The respondents were selected purposely and administered with the guided interview for the data collection.

Figure 1: Political map of the Accra Metropolitan Authority

The Educational map of the Accra Metropolitan Authority catchment area covers communities such as Kaneshie, Adabraka, Mamprobi, Mpoase, Chorkor, Korle-Gonno, and Accra Central. Please see Figure 1 for a political map of the Accra Metropolitan Authority.

Study population

The population for research work is a pooling of all kinds of individuals, substances, or dimensions of interest to the researcher. The population for the study, therefore, comprised all the teachers of Mamprobi Sempe 1 Basic School from Class One to Class Six.

Sample size and sampling techniques

Levy and Lemeshow (2013) describe the sampling process as selecting a part representing the general study populace. For this study, the researcher used a purposive sampling technique to collect data from respondents. Purposive sampling, also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in their study (Sharma 2017). The researcher used purposive sampling to permit respondents to be picked based on how they could answer particular questions based on the study's objectives.

All (30) teachers who taught at the basic level (i.e., from Class One to Class Six) at the Mamprobi Sempe 1 Basic School were selected for the data administration. The population constituted 16 female and 14 male teachers. Participants were selected because the researcher considered them to be the teaching group that plays a critical role in the early development stages of students; therefore, their responses were critical for the data collection exercise.

Data collection

Data collection for research work is the procedure of gathering necessary data from the chosen respondents of the study. Therefore, primary data was used for this research work. Data was collected through a structured interview. Interviews are the most effective data collection method because they help the researcher better understand participants' opinions, behaviours, and

experiences. Because interview questions are usually open-ended, participants can provide in-depth information. Interviews have a better response rate than questionnaires or mailed questions.

Data analysis

Collected data were analyzed, edited, and reviewed to remove ambiguity. Responses gathered from the data collection process were open to analysis, discussion, and interpretation based on the study's objective.

Findings and discussions

Types of incentives available in education

A well-motivated workforce is, undoubtedly, a results-oriented workforce. Attracting qualified individuals into the teaching profession, retaining qualified teachers, providing them with the necessary skills and knowledge, and motivating them to work hard and do their best is arguably the key education challenge. Research has demonstrated that even if faculty are interested in changing their pedagogical approach, few incentives are available to spur this action (Brownell and Tanner 2012). Incentives are motivational drivers: a major catalyst for optimal productivity in every sector, and education is no exception. Though the forms of incentives may vary from

sector to sector, the ultimate drive is the same throughout enhancing productivity. According to the participants, some incentives that could compensate teachers for their efforts could be in the form of scholarships, training and professional development programs, welfare, and health insurance schemes, promotions, lower teaching loads, financial benefits, recognition for tenure, teaching awards, or even, at the most basic level, verbal acknowledgment from colleagues and supervisors.

Financial benefits

With the perennial event of rising costs of living against the low remuneration of teachers, it is not only expedient for government and school administrators to pay teachers well to improve their teaching, but it is also a necessary intervention to stop the overwhelming neglect of the teaching profession by the youth for other well-paid professions. Financial rewards can attract many young people into teaching and sustain those already in the field. The fourth sustainable development goal seeks to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all by the year 2030. This goal cannot be achieved without teachers to teach our young people in schools.

The salaries of teachers, especially those in deplorable communities, need to be increased substantially so they can afford their basic needs. Financial incentives may be periodic yet not delayed raises, risk allowances, low-interest loans, subsidized accommodation, bonuses or gifts

in monetary terms, etc. It is abundantly clear these incentives cannot automatically improve teaching outcomes because there are teachers performing at the optimal level despite their hardships and those performing abysmally despite their satisfactory working conditions. Either of these is admissible, but if teachers give their best even in their deplorable states, their output could be significant if well-incentivized. A better livelihood invariably translates into a higher motivation for outstanding performance. Excellent performance also contributed extensively to producing quality students who contribute their skills, resources, and knowledge to nation-building.

Scholarships, training, and professional development programs

Scholarships are the instruments of encouragement towards education and research for teachers and students. Participants unanimously agreed that scholarships help more teachers to pursue higher studies without dependency on student loans which usually cripple the financial strength of teachers at the end of their study. The knowledge and research experience teachers acquire from sponsored education help them perform well in school. Teaching is dynamic, and the pedagogy of the profession is always shifting and incorporating new ideas and methods.

Employing ineffective or less effective teaching methods could have detrimental consequences on student learning. It could reduce motivation and increase negative attitudes towards learning, resulting in lower achievement (Biggs 1999). If teachers are stuck with old teaching methods,

they cannot meet new teaching demands to achieve their teaching outcomes. That is why it is necessary for schools to institute scholarship programs to assist teachers enrolling in higher education to acquire new knowledge and teaching methods.

In terms of training, participants indicated they feel ill-equipped to change how they teach. Thus, they want access to structured, formal training and professional development programs. Although it is quite difficult to gauge the long-term success of these programs, it is possible that there could be negative consequences for training teachers. Training comes with competence, and competence culminates in productivity.

Welfare programs, promotions, and award schemes

The provision of welfare programs such as health insurance (i.e., subsidized healthcare for certain categories of illnesses), emergency funds, etc., can contribute to a higher motivation for teachers towards work. According to participants, teachers are often overburdened with the workload. However, they are rarely granted leaves and opportunities to go for medical check-ups, which contributes to the deteriorating health of many teachers, especially those in rural communities with no access to quality healthcare. Also, the burden of footing high healthcare costs with inadequate salaries can disincentive teachers' performance. A weak or ill-prone workforce is likely to affect productivity, and often the resultant effect is increased teacher absenteeism and low performance of the students.

The incentive of granting teachers promotions when it is due to them is also a reinforcement tool. Like every worker, one of the job satisfactions of every teacher is the acknowledgement of their role by their superiors, which translates into their promotion in the institution's organizational structure. When teachers stagnate at their levels despite their experience, long service, or pursuit of higher studies, it leads to certain negative behavioral traits such as indifference towards work, absenteeism, bitterness, lackadaisical posture, etc., that could affect teaching and students' learning. A promoted teacher feels important and is motivated to increase their performance.

Employees who feel praised and valued often go on to achieve beyond expectations. They are the ones with the highest level of motivation, productivity, and morale. Recognition builds loyalty in the employees. Recognition improves employee retention. Teachers can be awarded for long service, best performance, innovation, industriousness, etc. Institutional recognition and collegial support seem to be considered incentives and essential requirements for improving teaching (Faremi 2021). The concept of extrinsic motivation proves this assertion. Most humans like compliments and acknowledgments. Therefore, using various forms of extrinsic motivation makes them change their behavior towards a particular direction. Most teachers believe creating rewards and incentives for teaching well and the improvement of teaching can significantly impact the value of and engagement in activities related to the improvement of teaching. Empirical studies have also affirmed the positive impact of teaching

awards on enhancing the quality of teaching and recognition of teaching in higher education institutions (Fabrice 2010).

Other external factors that can affect teaching outcome

The need for training and incentives are the most commonly cited impediments to achieving teaching outcomes at the basic level in most public schools; however, they need to be reconsidered. Imagine all schools provided teachers with all the training and all the incentives teachers needed; would that be enough to improve teaching outcomes in all schools? There is no adequate research to prove this. Although incentives are likely to cause a positive change, it is far from clear that they are sufficient in themselves for it to happen. According to participants, focusing efforts exclusively on training and incentives ignores additional and potentially key barriers to teacher and student performance: (a) the lack of teaching and learning materials (TLMs), (b) an effective teaching evaluation system, and (c) a conducive learning environment.

Provision of teaching and learning materials

The pivot of teaching and learning largely depends on the availability of TLMs to teachers. TLMs refer to a spectrum of classroom educational materials that teachers use to support specific learning objectives as set out in lesson plans. Instructional materials may aid a student in concretizing a learning experience to make learning more exciting, engaging, and interactive.

They are tools used in instructional activities, which include active learning and assessment.

Activity-based learning employs a variety of teaching/learning materials and focuses on student interaction to learn new concepts. Context-specific learning materials enhance the process. Some examples of TLMs are computers, projectors, visual aids, flashcards, games, videos, etc. Without TLMs, teachers may be unable to achieve their teaching outcomes regardless of being incentivized.

Institution of Effective Teaching Evaluation Systems

Teacher evaluation has proven to be one of the useful mechanisms to check teachers' performance. Evaluation systems must be able to differentiate between different teachers' effectiveness and apply that information in crucial personnel decisions to build the strongest possible teacher workforce. For example, in the past, many teacher evaluation systems included only two rating levels, satisfactory and unsatisfactory, with almost all teachers earning the former. This kind of evaluation is inadequate. Teacher evaluation systems should not only be based on teacher observations by a principal or a supervisor; more evaluation systems should factor in objective measures of student growth and other measures, such as student input in the form of surveys. The goals of effective teacher evaluation systems, when paired with supports and incentives, are designed to do the following: (a) provide a more valid measure of teacher quality by distinguishing between teachers at different performance levels, (b) recognize strong

teachers and keep them in the classroom, (c) encourage consistently less effective teachers to leave the classroom, (d) help all teachers improve, (e) recruit more effective new teachers, and (f) achieve gains in student learning and other positive student outcomes.

Creation of a conducive learning environment

A conducive learning environment is an atmosphere devoid of physical intimidation and emotional frustration that allows for a free exchange of ideas between teachers and learners. The freedom of interaction, safety, and respect of both learners and teachers should be equally guaranteed in the physical environment they find themselves in, and the classroom should be neat, well-ventilated, and spacious to allow for free movement. Creating the physical space, getting the students to cooperate, creating a communal environment, and maintaining a positive classroom climate and culture are requirements for improving teaching outcomes.

Conclusions and recommendations

Conclusion

One of the primary steps toward quality teaching is to enhance teachers' pedagogical skills. This can be achieved through merit-based incentives such as scholarships, training, and teacher professional development programs. The results of this study confirm existing literature that

merit-based incentives positively affect teacher performance and help improve teaching and learning outcomes. The outcome also extends the argument that effective teaching can stimulate and enhance learning while ineffective teaching can be detrimental to student studies (Brown and Atkins 2002). Both proponents and sceptics generally agree that teacher incentives change teacher behavior. Students in incentive schools performed significantly better than those with the least incentivized teachers. The study also noted other factors that might prove to be equally crucial to the success of teaching in many contexts. Some factors were considered, such as a lack of TLMs, a practical teaching evaluation system, and a conducive learning environment.

Recommendations

To improve teaching outcomes, the following recommendations are given by the researcher about the study: (a) adopt merit-based and unbiased teaching incentives, (b) provide TLMs, (c) institute effective teaching evaluation systems, (d) create a conducive learning environment, minimize teaching workload, and (f) establish supportive parent-teacher associations.

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The author declares that there is no conflict of interest.

Data availability statement

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author,

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Figure 1. Political map of the Accra Metropolitan Authority.